

Supplementary material to Coherence of COVID-19 mortality of Spain versus western European countries

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Abstract. The mortality impact of COVID-19 across European countries is a complex phenomenon influenced by political, social, economic, and environmental factors. The western European countries have implemented similar policies, with some specific divergences, like in the implementations of lockdowns and vaccination passes, so that similar results were to be expected. In this supplementary, the consideration of the structure of spatio-temporal peaks of mortality waves contributes to the impression that the COVID-19 mortality is a complex phenomenon resulting from the non-linear interaction of many factors, including political decisions as well as pharmaceutical and non-pharmaceutical interventions that should be the object of further studies.

Keywords: Wavelet coherence, COVID-19, Propagation

1 Introduction

The COVID-19 virus spread was quick and global in the early stages of the pandemic after the declaration of the WHO of the global health emergency. Simultaneous outbreaks happened in geographically distant locations such as Australia, United Kingdom, Israel, and United States. So the first wave was presented in the media as a global synchronous event, though some countries didn't show the sudden first wave in the period of March to May of the year 2020. Many modeling and research efforts were concentrated in the prediction of the number of cases in the early days of the pandemic with no great success [1]. Prediction of initial pseudo-exponential increase was easy with linear models, but after a while the picture turned quite chaotic, as can be ascertained upon inspection of Figure 1.

In this study we attempted to understand how the virus has been diffused across nations. A variety of factors, including social, economic, and environmental ones, have an impact on the spread of COVID-19, making it a complex phenomenon. Specifically, it is not evident the impact of the diverse policies adopted by different nations which also have adopted slightly different testing and reporting practices. It is challenging to compare COVID-19 mortality data between nations in order to assess the dynamics of the virus transmission.

2 Data and code

The pandemic-related data used in this study has been downloaded in January 1, 2023 from the website ourworldindata.com, which hosts a wide range of publicly available databases containing information on various aspects of the pandemic across multiple countries. These databases include data on cases, deaths, testing, vaccination rates, and other pertinent pandemic metrics that have been harvested by this website from official sources. The data and the matlab code has been publicised in the Zenodo open access repository (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7908439>).

Figure 1 plots the relative-to-population COVID-19 mortality time series of western Europe countries since January 1st, 2020 until the beginning of 2023 when the data for this study was downloaded. The graph depicts the deaths per million of COVID-19 for each country in the region, smoothed using a 14-day moving average. The figure provides a visual representation of the pandemic impact on Europe. We have signaled in the plot the approximate time location of the peaks of the mortality waves in Spain that are used as reference for the comparative study of the mortality in other western Europe countries.

Fig. 1. Relative COVID-19 mortality daily time series of western Europe countries (deaths per million, fourteen days moving average) since January 1st, 2020 until January 1st, 2023. Red font W_n marks the approximate time of the n -th wave peak in the Spanish COVID-19 mortality time series.

3 Results

3.1 Similarity among waves

The present analysis entails a comparison of the magnitude of each wave of the COVID-19 pandemic in Spain against its effect on the other countries. To this

end, the highest peaks of each wave have been selected as reference time points as shown in Figure 1. We consider the integral of the mortality time series (number of deaths per million) for a period of 61 days centered at these reference time points for each country. The reference points correspond to the following dates: 2nd April 2020 for the first wave (W1), 4th November 2020 for the second wave (W2), 8th February 2021 for the third wave (W3), 25th March 2021 for the fourth wave (W4), 23rd August 2021 for the fifth wave (W5), and 14th February 2022 for the sixth wave (W6). Figure 2 shows the bar plot with these integrals computed around each Spanish wave peak. This plot gives another view on the (absence of) synchronization among COVID-19 death time series. With a very similar sequence of interventions, Belgium shows quite different reponse. In the first and second wave the relative deaths in Belgium are well above Spain, however in the third wave they are half the deaths in Spain, and in the fifth are less that 25% of the Spanish deaths. Another interesting case is Portugal, which has less that 20% of the Spanish deaths in the first wave, while doubling them in the third wave. Italy has comparable death toll in all waves, while Switzerland has a similar reponse as Belgium, less dramatic in the second wave. One of the most noteworthy findings of the analysis pertains to the lack of synchronization of the mortality time series during the six waves of the pandemic. This observation implies that the severity and impact of the pandemic may be influenced by a variety of factors, including the gathering and reporting policies implemented in each country, which underscores the importance of analyzing the pandemic’s impact from a multidisciplinary perspective that incorporates various factors and perspectives.

Fig. 2. Number of deaths in the period of two months centered at each wave peak in the Spanish mortality time series that identified in Figure 1.

Table 1 provides a summary of the dynamics of the COVID-19 deaths given by time instant of the first cases and deaths reported, and the number of accumulated deaths in a period of 61 days centered at the wave peak day. The table provides the ranking number of each country for each measure. The table provides a view that is complementary to Figure 2. If we consider the successive rankings of the countries we have some surprises, such as Belgium going from the first position in the ranking of the first two waves to the last position in the third wave, or Sweden being in the last positions until the last wave when it becomes second in the ranking following Italy. Overall impression is that there is no spatio-temporal diffusion logic in the evolution of pandemic mortality, which raises questions about the underlying transmission mechanisms.

Table 1. Summary of the dynamics of the COVID-19 pandemic deaths in terms of first reported deaths and cases, and relative impact of the waves on each country. Waves are defined around the peaks in Spanish mortality curves identified in Figure 1. **time** refers the number of days since January 1, 2020; **frd** day of first reported death; **rfd** ranking in time of first death; **frc** day of first reported case; **rfc**: ranking in time of first reported case; **swn**: accumulated relative deaths in the n-th wave, **rwn**: ranking in accumulated relative deaths of the n-th wave.

	frd	rfd	frc	rfc	sw1	rw1	sw2	rw2	sw3	rw3	sw4	rw4	sw5	rw5	sw6	rw6
time n-th wave					92		101		404		449		600		775	
Spain	62	4	31	5	527.77	4	297.86	7	422.36	4	209.32	3	102.27	1	224.08	3
Andorra	81	10	61	11	551.09	3	300.59	5	350.69	7	187.87	4	37.57	6	125.25	8
Belgium	70	8	34	6	666.18	1	607.24	1	202.04	12	177.33	5	27.11	9	161.29	6
France	45	2	23	1	365.12	6	333.52	4	327.38	9	266.94	2	69.20	3	204.90	5
Germany	78	6	26	2	78.88	12	102.02	10	404.15	5	162.42	6	19.57	11	129.60	7
Italy	51	3	30	4	485.42	5	387.31	3	387.89	6	390.07	1	43.21	5	283.99	1
Portugal	76	9	60	10	99.60	11	272.42	7	878.89	1	91.13	11	65.14	4	204.95	4
UK	29	1	29	3	599.65	2	302.79	6	712.92	2	107.75	9	108.50	2	108.50	10
Netherlands	65	5	57	8	284.67	7	180.65	8	215.04	10	101.86	10	20.90	10	34.39	12
Sweden	69	7	31	5	274.99	8	111.95	9	346.37	8	120.76	8	15.07	12	229.78	2
Ireland	70	8	59	9	256.01	9	54.94	11	432.40	3	146.32	7	36.43	7	120.05	9
Switzerland	65	5	55	7	193.12	10	400.89	2	205.60	11	61.44	12	28.71	8	97.36	11

3.2 Comparing maximum values

The development of the pandemic in different countries can be analyzed by observing mortality peaks and their temporal distribution shown in Table 2. These peaks tell us whether there has been a spread of the virus and what the waves of the pandemic have been like in each country. For example, if a country experiences a mortality peak after another country has experienced it, we can infer that there has been a transmission of the virus between these countries. In this way, how the peaks are distributed over time can help us understand how

the waves of the pandemic have been spread and how they have been managed by their respective governments and health systems.

Upon reviewing the table, it becomes evident that countries such as Portugal and Andorra, which are geographically adjacent to Spain, did not experience a peak in the number of COVID-19 deaths near the same time as Spain. Instead, Andorra experienced its greatest peak towards the end of the pandemic. On the other hand, Netherlands, Belgium, Ireland, and France have relatively close in time maximum peaks accordingly to their geographical closeness. Notice that some countries, namely Germany, Portugal, United Kingdom, Sweden and Switzerland had their greatest mortality peaks after the deployment of the pharmaceutical intervention. There is

Table 2. Time localization of the maximum death peaks per country. **mdv**: maximum death relative-to-population value per country, **mdd**: days until mdv since January 1, 2020; **r**: ranking of mdv.

	mdv	mdd	r
Spain	34.13	308	5
Andorra	87.67	1084	12
Belgium	42.55	100	2
France	21.21	115	4
Germany	14.92	379	7
Italy	16.82	337	6
Portugal	29.50	393	10
UK	22.07	384	8
Netherlands	13.32	97	1
Sweden	44.93	385	9
Ireland	43.80	114	3
Switzerland	14.99	405	11

4 Conclusions

In some places and times, mortality peaks are significant and representative of the evolution of the pandemic. They can indicate whether there has been transmission or spread, whether there has been an original site, and whether it has spread to other locations. It is important to keep in mind that these mortality peaks have been displaced in time and that the detection of an original site keeps complicated. These findings imply that the correlation matrix does not provide a comprehensive depiction of the interrelationships between the variables, and the coherence measures may need to be complemented with other analytical tools or variables to yield a more comprehensive and accurate understanding of them.

The availability and dependability of data are one of the major difficulties in the research on the diffusion and spread of COVID-19. Moreover, the low

coherence correlations may warrant further investigation to ascertain the possible factors that could account for the observed patterns.

Acknowledgements

The work in this paper has been partially supported by FEDER funds for the MICIN project PID2020-116346GB-I00. Authors have received research funds from the Basque Government as the Grupo de Inteligencia Computacional, Universidad del Pais Vasco, UPV/EHU since 2007 until 2025. The current code for the grant is IT1689-22. Additionally, the authors are participating in Elkartek projects KK-2022/00051 and KK-2021/00070.

References

1. John P A Ioannidis, Sally Cripps, and Martin A Tanner. Forecasting for covid-19 has failed. *Int J Forecast*, 38(2):423–438, Apr-Jun 2022.